

Are Rural SACCOS in Tanzania Sustainable?

Author Detail: Joseph John Magali

Accounting School, Dongbei University of Finance and Economics, P.O. Box 116025, Dalian- China and The Open University of Tanzania, P. O. Box 23409, Dar es salaam, Tanzania

Abstract

Many rural projects and programmes in Tanzania flourish and diminish before and after phasing out of donors' facilitation respectively. This study applied the qualitative, descriptive and multivariate regression analysis to investigate whether the rural Savings and Credits Cooperative Societies (SACCOS) in Eastern, Central and Northern zones of Tanzania were still sustainable after the phasing out of capacity building projects in 2013. The study also examined the outreach level of the rural SACCOS since their establishment. The study revealed that 46% of SACCOS in rural Tanzania especially in Eastern and central zone were not sustainable because they accumulated large amount of NPL and they did not issue new loans from 2006-2013. The study further revealed that savings and deposits to total assets influenced the outreach negatively while cost per borrower and OSS influenced the outreach positively. On the other hand, grants to total loans, cost per borrower, NPL to equity influenced the sustainability of rural SACCOS negatively while average loan size and age of SACCOS influenced the sustainability of rural SACCOS positively. This study recommends that the rural SACCOS in Tanzania should devise various strategies to achieve financial sustainability such as volunteering labour, accumulate high amounts of own equity in forms of shares, collect the NPL from members and apply credit risks management techniques including insurance coverage to reduce the NPL. Finally, I call for policy action to review the operations of the rural SACCOS and establish the stringent regulations and supervisions by the government.

Keywords: Rural SACCOS, outreach, Sustainability, Tanzania

1.1 Introduction

Savings and Credits Cooperatives Societies (SACCOS) in Tanzania have been established formally since 1980s. In Tanzania SACCOS play great role in fostering social economic development of both urban and rural areas (Bwana and Mwakujonga 2013; Qin and Ndiege 2013). The role of SACCOS in rural area is more extended because there are no formal financial institutions providing the financial services (Wangwe 2004). Therefore, recently SACCOS remain the semiformal financial institutions which provide the small loans to many members in rural areas of Tanzania. The government of Tanzania has realized that SACCOS are vital for promoting social economic development of Tanzania hence provides the supervisory services to enhance their expansion. Up to March 2013 and 2011 the government registered 5346 SACCOS which have more than 970665 members (MOFT, 2012; 2013). Hakikazi (2006), Bibby (2006), Maghimbi (2010), Mwakajumilo (2011), Karumuna and Akyoo (2011) and Magali (2013b) noted that the poor management, fraud and high Non Performing Loans (NPL) are the main problems which threatens the outreach and sustainability of the rural SACCOS in Tanzania.

Outreach refers to how MFIs expanded their services to their members or clients. Mariya et al (2007) defined outreach as the number of loans provided to poor borrowers. Schreiner (2002) and Pradhan (n.d) argued that the complete study of outreach should focus on all

of its six aspects: worth, cost, depth, breadth, length and scope which are defined as the willingness to pay, sum of price (interest and fees) costs and transaction costs, value that society attaches to the net gain of a given (poor) clients, number of clients, time frame (continuity) of the supply of MFIs services and both loans (contracts for group and individuals) and savings services respectively.

Most scholars use similar variables when measuring depth and breadth outreach. Mostly, breadth of outreach is measured by the number of clients benefited from MFI or the number of borrowers while the depth of outreach is measured by the number of clients who accessed credits preferably the poor people. However, because unavailability of data, average loan balances per borrower is mostly used for measuring the depth of outreach by most authors (Sarma and Borbora 2011; Schreiner 2002; Seibel and Parhusip 1998; Mohammed 2011; Ndiege et al 2013), to mention few. The theory of outreach contends that the poorer the borrowers are served by the MFIs, the better the outreach. Hence MFIs are encouraged to increase their outreach by providing relatively small loans (Schreiner 2002; Jegede et al 2012; Osotimehin et al 2011; Kailthya n.d).

According to Woller et al (1999), sustainability implies institutional permanence. Schreiner (2002) and Gingrich (n.d) stressed that sustainable MFI will continue to provide the financial services in future. Sustainability

usually is measured by Operational Self Sufficiency (OSS) ratio which measures the degree to which operating income covers operating expenses or Financial Self Sufficiency (FSS) ratio which measures the degree to which operating income covers both operational and financial expenses (Yaron and Manos 2007). Nyamsogoro (2010) and Yaron and Manos (2007) argued that if the FSS measure is below 100% the MFI is defined as subsidy dependent while when adjusted income exceeds adjusted cost, the MFI is defined as self-sufficient (subsidy independent). Scholars differ in views when explaining the important of donors' subsidies to enhance the sustainability of MFI where some of them oppose while others recommend. Schreiner (2002) argues that attainment of self-sufficiency is important for reducing the reliance on donor funds while Pradhan (n.d) stressed that a MFI may be financially sustainable if it can attract a constant flow of subsidized funds over time so as to reduce financial costs and earn profit.

Some scholars relates the outreach and sustainability concepts altogether. Schreiner (2002) asserted that, there two approaches of outreach; the poverty and self sufficiency approach and concentrating too much on MFIs self sustainability and in this way escaping to serve the very poor is regarded as the mission drift. However, good repayment of loans should be emphasized because it promotes self-sustainability as opposed to loans default which threatens self-sustainability of MFIs. Hermes (2009) argued that attaining financial sustainability can curtail the outreach of MFI to the poor people and this is called the trade-off between sustainability and outreach. Most scholars revealed the existence of tradeoff between outreach and sustainability of MFIs (Zeller and Meyer 2002; Onumah and Acquah 2011; Sheremenko et al 2012; Roy (2012) Kipesha and Zhang 2013) while few scholars found no tradeoff between outreach and profitability (Zerai and Rani 2013; Quayes 2012).

1.2 Problem statement and Justification

Rural SACCOS are important engine for economic development in Tanzania (Bwana and Mwakujonga 2013; Qin and Ndiege 2013). Hence they are supposed be sustainable in order to continue their enormous contribution to economic growth of the Tanzania and serve the rural populations. However, expanding the services to very poor and neglected people should not be exchanged with sustainability focus. Therefore continuous studying of rural SACCOS is essential for examining their status on both outreach and sustainability. Some studies have been conducted in East Africa and Tanzania in particular to assess the outreach

and sustainability of MFIs and SACCOS. Kipesha and Zhang (2013) examined the presence of MFIs tradeoffs between sustainability, profitability and outreach of MFIs in East Africa where their study generalized for all MFIs. However, they revealed the tradeoffs between the outreach and profitability. Nyamsogoro (2010) studied the financial sustainability of rural MFIs which included SACCOS, Savings and Credits Associations (SACAS), Non cooperative MFIs and NGOs. The study was done in Northern, Central and Southern Zone. Temu and Ishengoma (2010) applied the quantitative analysis to examine the effect of financial linkages, sustainability and the outreach of rural SACCOS in Tanzania. The research was done in Central, Northern and Southern Highlands zones (Dodoma, Kilimanjaro and Mbeya regions) in 2006. Ndiege et al (2013) studied the relationship between sources of funds and outreach in savings and credits cooperatives societies in Tanzania. The study focused on outreach and it combined both urban and rural SACCOS.

This study considers the study by Temu and Ishengoma (2010), who studied the outreach and sustainability of rural SACCOS in 2006. It should be noted that in 2006 most SACCOS in Tanzania including those in Eastern, Central and Northern zones (Morogoro, Dodoma and Kilimanjaro regions) received subsidies from the projects which promoted the rural SACCOS in form of training, funds and facilitation of the government officers who supervised the rural SACCOS. Hence Temu and Ishengoma (2010) conducted their study when many SACCOS received help from the project known as Rural Financial Service Program (RFSP) and the study was done in Central, and Southern Highlands and Northern zones of Tanzania (Dodoma, Mbeya and Kilimanjaro regions). It should be also noted that most projects which helped to build the capacities of the rural SACCOS, phased out in 2010s. Therefore this paper analyzes the sustainability of rural SACCOS in Tanzania after the phasing out of many projects which helped the rural SACCOS in various ways. This study also considers the Eastern part of Tanzania which was not considered by other authors who studied the outreach and sustainability of the rural SACCOS. Therefore, this study was done in East, Central and Northern parts of Tanzania specifically Morogoro, Dodoma and Kilimanjaro regions. The main question which will be answered at the end of article is: **Are rural SACCOS in Tanzania recently sustainable?**

2.0 Literature review

2.1 Empirical literature on Outreach and Sustainability

Various authors studied outreach and sustainability of MFIs where OSS and FSS and average loan size and number of borrowers or female borrowers were used to measure outreach and sustainability respectively. Kumar and Gupta (2011) found out that South Asian MFIs had higher values of OSS and FSS than the East Asian and Pacific region MFIs. The study further revealed that the financial expenses were more important for the MFIs in South Asian MFIs than the operational expenses. Also the regression analysis indicated that the average loan per borrower, Returns on Assets (ROA) and Portfolio at risk were the major influencers of the OSS while capital asset utilization influenced the FSS in both regions. Thapa (n.d) revealed that the MFIs in the South East Asian and South Asian earned the positive and negative ROA and returns on equity (ROE) respectively, indicating that MFIs in the first region were more financial sustainable compared to the other region. The study justified the receipt of subsidies, reduction of operational costs and charging of market interest rates for MFIs which serve the poor in remote rural areas in order to achieve financial self-sufficiency and expand outreach. Hartarska (n.d) used a panel data from 250 MFIs in the world for the period 1998-2011 to estimate the technical and outreach efficiency. The study noted that MFIs with female CEOs have 12-14% points higher outreach efficiency. Jegede et al (2012) observed the increasing trends of outreach and sustainability (OSS) of the MFIs in Nigeria over time. It was further noted that group-based loan delivery method was the most important determinant of sustainability. Nonetheless, the study revealed that neglecting of agricultural loans for rural people for six years was the threat for outreach. Kinde (2012) found that microfinance breadth of outreach, depth of outreach; dependency ratio and cost per borrower affect the financial sustainability of microfinance institutions in Ethiopia.

Zaigham and Asghar (2011) measured the financial sustainability of Microfinance Banks (MFBs) in Pakistan during the flood disaster in 2009-2010 by using OSS, ROA and transaction cost per borrower. The study revealed the net decrease of - 2.46% and -4.46% of adjusted ROA and OSS of MFBs respectively after the floods event, indicating the decline of MFBs sustainability because lenders were not able to repay the loans. Osotimehin et al (2011) used the regression model to examine the determinants and trend of outreach of microfinance institutions in Nigeria. The study noted that outreach was positively determined by average loan size, debt-equity ratio, loan repayment rates and salaries. Kailthya (n.d) revealed that there is interdependence between financial sustainability and outreach of Indian MFIs where operational efficiency, leverage and

institutional structure affected the financial performance while outreach was determined by better motivated staff, management of risks and reduction in operational costs. The correlation test also indicated a significantly negative and high correlation between percent of women borrowers and average loan balance per borrower while ROA and ROE and average loan balance per borrower were positively correlated and ROA and ROE and operational expenses to assets were negatively correlated, implying that the higher cost per borrower restricted the expansion of MFIs outreach. Sarma and Borbora (2011) examined the outreach and sustainability by using FSS, Subsidy Dependence Index (SDI) and Subsidy Dependence Ratio (SDR) and noticed that although MFIs in Assam-India had greater outreach, they were still financially not self-sufficient. The study further revealed that about 90% of the borrowers were women and the average size of loan grew by 23.1% and OSS was more than 100%, indicating that the MFIs compensated their operational costs. However, the analysis further noted that as SDI increases, OSS, FSS and outreach shrunk.

Conning (2009) argued that always there is a tradeoff between outreach and financial sustainability because reaching the poorest of the poor is more costly. The study further argued that considering sustainability is important because currently even donors and policy makers are interested with the financial sustainability of the MFIs. The study stressed that the sustainability today will promote more leverage, outreach and impact of the MFIs tomorrow. Seibel and Parhusip (1998) revealed that one self-financed private village bank in Indonesia (Bank Shinta Daya) increased profits, viability, sustainability and outreach to the poor because it employed both the individual and group lending technologies. They stressed that Bank Shinta Daya had demonstrated that privately owned village banks can have a substantial outreach at the local level without receiving concessionary funds, since the group lending technology enabled the recruitment of 69% and 85% of poor borrowers and savers respectively. Also it has enabled the doubling of its outreach and growth of capital from US\$ 40,000 to US\$ 215,000 from 1970 to 1995 respectively.

Temu and Ishengoma (2010) applied the regression model to examine the effect of financial linkages on income generation and the outreach of rural SACCOs in Tanzania. The results revealed that internal finance and location of SACCOS have a significant contribution to breadth of outreach and sustainability of SACCOS while the relationship between financial linkages on SACCOS' breadth and depth of outreach and sustainability was not

significant. Nyamsogoro (2010) by using correlation and multiple regression model found out that high interest rate and large loan size promoted financial sustainability, high cost per borrower reduced financial sustainability while age of MFI, number of borrowers and female clients didn't promote financial sustainability and northern and southern Tanzania were related with financial sustainability of rural MFI (NGOs, SACCOS and SACAS) in Tanzania. Also the study found out that average loan size and staff cost per borrower was positively correlated while maturity for group lending was correlated with the number of installments. Mohammed (2011) revealed that there was a significant positive relationship between financing strategies, financial sustainability and outreach of SACCOS. Results from the regression analysis showed that financing strategies and financial sustainability significantly predicted 56.1% of outreach of SACCOS in Uganda. Ndiege al (2013) examined the linkage between sources of funds and level of outreach of SACCOS in Tanzania by using panel data and regression model. The study revealed that external sources were becoming central part of the SACCOS loan portfolio compared to internal sources of funds. Sebhatu (2011) revealed that there was improvement of outreach (measured by membership) and financial performance of the SACCOS. The result indicated the strong positive correlation between financial performance (ROA) and the asset utilization whereas a moderate positive correlation relationship was found between operational efficiency and size of SACCOS (assets size) and the significant negative correlation was observed between financial performance (ROA) and the operational efficiency in Ethiopia. Gingrich (n.d) revealed that nearly all Savings and credit cooperatives in Nepali (SCCs) even those in poor and remote areas were profitable because they were self-funded using member savings and equity, controlled the administrative costs (used only 5% of total assets) and collected the reasonable interest income. For promoting the sustainability of SCCs, the author recommended that the government and donors should concentrate more on institution building and should not provide grants.

Hermes (2009) argued that when considering financial sustainability of MFIs the debate between outreach and sustainability arises showing a tradeoff between sustainability and outreach. The study concluded that higher levels of outreach of MFI should be reached without compromising its financial sustainability. Roy (2012) revealed the tradeoff between outreach and financial the performance (ROA) of MFIs at Assam-India. Also the study noted that average ROA and ROE declined as the number of active loan clients increased

beyond 2000 indicating that serving a large number of clients reduced the efficiency of MFIs. Zeller and Meyer (2002) found that in Mexico because of lower costs wealthier individuals received more credit than the poorest. They argued that the concept of the triangle of outreach, financial sustainability and impact is of important consideration by all MFIs, because always broader and deeper outreach to the poor tradeoff with financial sustainability. The study further revealed that in Latin America there was a positive correlation between reliance on subsidies and the breadth of outreach. However in Malawi, farming efficiency through accessing credit was only associated with better farming technology. Onumah and Acquah (2011) noticed that that the outreach of the inventory credit programme (ICP) in Ghana in terms of loan size/GNP per capita and percentage of women clients expanded from 25-47% and 20-39% respectively. However, a comparative analysis of two successful MFIs indicated that the ICP did not perform well in reaching the very poor while it was financially sustainable because of high loan recovery rate. The study also noted the presence of a trade-off between outreach to the poorest and a financial sustainability of the ICP. Hermes et al (2008) by using the stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) noted the existence of a trade-off between outreach to the poor and efficiency of MFIs, implying that MFIs which had more women borrowers were less efficient worldwide. Sheremenko et al (2012) noted that MFIs performance in Russia, the Caucasus, and Central Asia were profit-driven and paid less attention to outreach. The study noted that 75% of MFIs were financial self-sufficient and 85% of for-profit MFIs were financially self-sufficient. Kipesha and Zhang (2013) noted that under Welfarists approach it was found that profitability has a negative impact on outreach to the poor, implying the presence of tradeoffs while under Institutionalists view, the study found out that outreach to the poor has a positive relationship with both MFIs sustainability and profitability in East Africa. They concluded that the presence of tradeoffs between financial performance and outreach to the poor also depends on the variables used and model specification.

However, few studies did not recognize the tradeoff between outreach and sustainability. Zerai and Rani (2013) did not recognize a tradeoff between outreach and financial sustainability of Indian MFIs because the correlation between average loan size, the number of women borrowers and operational sustainability was found to be weak. However, the study revealed the strong positive correlation between the number of active borrowers and operational sustainability. Quayes (2012) revealed a positive complementary relationship between

financial sustainability and depth of outreach. The study contends that the primary justification for subsidizing of (MFIs) is extending credit to the poor households. Also the study noticed that for-profit MFIs had better operational sustainability with large average loan per borrower than their nonprofit counterparts which had better outreach. Kereta (2007) examined the outreach and financial performance analysis of MFIs in Ethiopia. The study revealed that the outreach rose by an average of 22.9% from 2003 to 2007 where 38.4% of women were served and operational sustainability was measured by ROA and ROE and the profit performance improved over time since dependency ratio and Non-performing Loan (NPLs) to loan outstanding ratio indicated that MFIs were financial sustainable. However, the evidence of trade-off between outreach and financial sustainability was not confirmed.

Some scholars revealed that factors such as gender, regulations, occupations and Management Information (MIS) also influence the outreach and sustainability of MFIs. Cull et al (2009) revealed that supervision is negatively associated with profitability and outreach indicating that despite supervision increases average loan sizes, it increases costs and curtail financial services to poor women worldwide. Sahoo and Mishra (2012) revealed that majority of the MFIs didn't use the information technology to achieve higher outreach in India because of a shortage of skilled professionals and high costs. Hartarska and Nadolnyak (2007) found that in 62 countries in the world regulations did not directly affect performance (OSS) or outreach of MFIs. The study further revealed that less leveraged MFIs had better sustainability, suggesting that savings was vital for MFIs. Babandi (2011) by using the Likert scale revealed that outreach performance and sustainability of microfinance institutions in Nigeria covered all gender, locations and occupations indicating that there were no significant differences between outreach and sustainability and specified variables.

2.2 Variables for measuring Outreach and Sustainability

Various authors use different variables for measuring the outreach and sustainability of MFI and SACCOS. Temu and Ishengoma (2010) used the membership growth, membership size, loan size, and interest income as a measure of breadth of outreach, depth of outreach and sustainability of rural SACCOS in Tanzania respectively because data for other variables were not available. Mohammed (2011) measured financial sustainability of SACCOS (debt and equity financing and individual savings), in terms of operational and financial self-sustainability while outreach was measured in terms of

depth and breadth which were proxied by average loan size and the logarithm of active borrowers respectively. Ndiege al (2013) applied two similar models to examine the outreach where dependent variables were the number of members of SACCOS and average credits for breadth and depth respectively. The independent variables were credits per assets, external source of funds, internal sources of funds (shares, deposits and savings) and external-internal sources ratio, age of SACCOS, number of SACCOS and credits per assets ratio which was used to check its impact on outreach. Kinde (2012) considered FSS as dependent variable while the independent variables were: log of number of borrowers, average loan size, debt to equity, donated equity to total capital, cost per borrower and borrowers per staff. Similarly, Nyamsogoro (2010) used dependent variable as FSS while the independent variables were: MFIs capital structure (equity/capital), interest rates, difference in lending type (group or individual), cost per borrower, product type, MFI size, age, number of borrowers (as proxy for outreach), female clients, yield on gross loan portfolio, level of portfolio risk, liquidity level, staff productivity, and operating model (regulated vs non regulated). Average loan size was used as a proxy measure for outreach while the Size of MFI was measured by total assets. Also because of difficulty in assessing data, authors measured depth of outreach by assessing the relationship between number of borrowers and profitability instead of using the poor clients for rural SACCOS, NGOs and SACAS in Tanzania.

Hartarska and Nadolnyak (2007) used OSS to measure MFIs self-sufficiency while outreach was measured by the logarithm of the number of active borrowers. Other independent variables used were: a dummy of regulation, registration status as an NGO, existence of deposit insurance and being a legal English origin, common number of sources of capital, indices of officials power, size of the informal market, protection of property right, economic freedom and government intervention, logarithm of GDP in 1995 price equivalent and the total assets (size), number of MFI competitors in the country, ratio of total equity to total assets, saving to total assets and loans outstanding to total assets, age and age squared of the MFI, the percentage of change of the GDP deflator and GDP per capita. Hermes et al (2008) used woman borrowers and average loan balance per borrower as outreach variables. Other variables were: loan type (individual, group and village loans), year and age of MFIs. Quayes (2012) used the dependent variable as average loan balance per borrower divided by Gross National Income, FSS and OSS while the independent variables were: gross loan portfolio in US dollars, total equity in US dollars, debt to equity ratio, total expense

ratio, cost of loan per borrower and number of women borrowers as a fraction of total number of borrowers. Kipesha and Zhang (2013) treated independent variables (proxies for sustainability and profitability of MFIs) as OSS, ROA, yield on gross loan, operating expenses to asset ratio, financial revenue to gross loan portfolio ratio, gross loan to asset ratio, debt to equity ratio, cost per borrower ratio and borrowers per staff ratio. The study applied three similar models where the dependent variables were: average loan balance per capital, percentage of women borrowers and number of active borrowers. Kailthya (n.d) considered the dependent variable as average loan balance per borrower as proxy for depth of outreach. The independent variables were: cost per borrower, cost per loan (USD), operating expense/assets, debt to equity ratio, age of MFI (in years), percent of women borrowers, % ROA, % ROE, borrowers per staff member, yield on gross portfolio (real), portfolio at risk > 30 days (%). Osotimehin et al (2011) treated the number of clients of MFIs as dependent variable for outreach while the independent

variables were: debt equity ratio representing division of source of capital to a microfinance institution, management skills, real effective lending interest rate, average loan size, cost of loans disbursed, loan delivery method, ownership status, loan repayment rate, age of MFI, savings and salary/wages and other benefits paid to labour.

3.0 Methods

This study involved 37 rural SACCOS from Eastern, Central and Northern zones (Morogoro, Dodoma and Kilimanjaro regions) in Tanzania between February and May 2013. The data used for this study collected both by using the structured questionnaires and extracts from the SACCOS financial reports. This study applied qualitative, descriptive and two separate multivariate regression models to analyse the outreach and sustainability of the rural SACCOS in Tanzania. The outreach model is measured by the logarithm of average loan size (breadth) where the regression equation was constructed as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \mu$$

Where; is the Y-intercept, β_0 is the Beta coefficient of X_n variable and μ is the error term. The regression model was used to assess how the independent factors affect outreach of rural SACCOS' borrowers in Tanzania and the variables are defined as:

- X₁- Savings and deposits to total assets
- X₂- Age of SACCOS
- X₃- Log of cost per borrower
- X₄-OSS

The study noted that measuring outreach by using women borrowers (depth) was not significant while Sustainability was measured by OSS where the model was constructed as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + \mu \text{ Where:}$$

- X₁- NPL to Equity
- X₂- Log of cost per borrower
- X₃- Age of SACCOS
- X₄- Grants to Total Loans
- X₅- Log of average loan size

Since the data used was cross sectional, the author considered the assumptions of multivariate linear regression models to make sure that there are no serious problems of autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity and multicollinearity. Furthermore, the model choice followed institutionalists paradigm as categorized by Zaigham and Asghar (2011).

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 The results of outreach variables from the regression equation

The results from the regression equation are displayed on Table 1 where the coefficients of R-square, F-statistics, standard error and Durbin Watsons show that the variables fit the equation very well. The findings show that only cost per borrower, OSS and savings and deposits to total assets significantly influence the outreach, measured by log average loan size. The findings further show that the cost per borrower influence outreach positively, implying that in order the rural

SACCOS to reach the large number of clients, including the women borrowers and the very poor, it has to incur high costs. This truth was also confirmed by Magali and Pastory (2013), where it was revealed that the rural SACCOS in Tanzania are not efficient because they incur higher cost of operations. Similarly, Nyamsogoro (2010) found out that rural financial institutions (SACCOS, SACAS and NGOs) reached clients at higher costs. However, Kailthya, (n.d) revealed that the cost per borrower included in the outreach equation and was significantly negative, implying that MFIs outreach expanded at reduced cost per borrower in India.

The findings from Table 1 also show that the outreach increases with the increase of financial performance measured by OSS. The findings indicate that only SACCOS with good financial performance sustained the outreach. This was very obvious during the survey where it was noted that some SACCOS' members dropped out from SACCOS and joined Village Community Banks (VICOBA) because the SACCOS couldn't provide loans to them due to lack of funds, after accumulating large amount of Non Performing Loans (NPL). This result was confirmed by Kipesha and Zhang (2013) who noted that average loan size and OSS for MFIs in Tanzania and East Africa was significantly and positively correlated. Similarly, Abate et al (2013) found that there was a positive causation between OSS and average loan size for MFIs in Ethiopia. On the contrary, Quayes (2011) found no effect of financial performance on outreach for MFIs located in 83 countries worldwide.

Likewise, the findings show that savings and deposits to total assets affect outreach negatively. This result is in tandem with Kumar and Gupta (2011) who revealed that the average loan balance per borrower was fairly higher for the MFIs which did not practice savings. This study noted that savings and deposits reduces outreach because they belong to members and hence the rural SACCOS incurred higher costs to administer them, since it was found that higher costs reduce the strengths of outreach. Also the rural SACCOS' members were free to withdraw their savings and deposits at any time; hence the SACCOS couldn't rely on members' savings and deposits for running the rural SACCOS. Moreover, study noted that many rural SACCOS used members' savings and deposits to recover the loans during the loans default. Furthermore, SACCOS which accumulated large amount of NPL used members' savings and deposits to operate the SACCOS. Thus members with savings and deposits were not paid their money when requested the payments from SACCOS and hence were discouraged and decided to leave the rural SACCOS. However, both Nyamsogoro (2010) and Ndiege (2013) emphasized that savings and deposits are important for SACCOS because they create the sense of ownership to members and they increase the capital. Similarly, Gingrich (n.d) revealed that in Nepal equity financing enabled Community-Based Savings and Credit Cooperatives to become self sufficient where the study recorded the mean savings-to-asset ratios over 70%. Moreover, Temu and Ishengoma (2010) revealed that internal finance (shares, savings and deposits) significantly contributed to the sustainability of the rural of SACCOS in Tanzania.

Table 1: Regression coefficients for of outreach (measured by log average loan size)

Independent variables	Estimated value of coefficients	t-value
Log cost per borrower	1.032*	13.53
OSS	0.467*	6.070
Age of SACCOS	-0.115***	-1.558
Savings and deposits to total assets	-0.183**	-2.449
Value of R ²	0.861	-
Adjusted R ²	0.843	-
Value of F	49.42*	
Durbin Watson	1.847	-
Standard Error of Estimate	0.14033	-

*Significant at 1% level; **significant at 5% level; ***Not significant

4.2 The results of sustainability variables from the regression equation

The findings of sustainability are presented in Table 2. The regression variables suggest that the variables fit the equation very well. Despite the study noted that almost grants received by the rural SACCOS were almost negligible, where it was noted that only about 10% of SACCOS received small amount of grants; the findings show that grants reduce the financial sustainability of the rural SACCOS. Since loans are a component of total assets for rural SACCOS, this result is supported by Bogan (2009) who revealed that grants per total assets influence negatively OSS. Similarly, Schreiner (2002) and

Conning (2009) discouraged the use of grants for MFI to become sustainable as opposed to Pradhan (n.d) who encouraged the receipt of grants especially for MFIs which serve the poor people in remote areas. Similarly, Seibel and Parhusip (1998) asserted that MFI can attain a significant outreach at the local level without receiving subsidies (or grants).

The findings also show that sustainability increases as the average loan size increases, indicating that, it is the large size of loans which makes the rural SACCOS sustainable or vice versa. It implies that the large size of loans lowers the operation costs for the rural SACCOS and hence increases the profitability. This result was also confirmed Nyamsogoro (2010) and Quayes (2012) who revealed that large size of loan improves the sustainability of MFI and SACCOS. Similarly, Hermes et al (2008) found out that MFIs that have lower average loan balances were also less efficient. However, Zerai and Rani (2013) found that the correlation between the average loan size and OSS for Indian MFIs was found to be weak. Additionally, Nyamsogoro (2010) and Magali (2013b) noted that disbursing high volume of loans it increases the default risks.

Moreover, the findings from Table 2 show that age of SACCOS affect positively the financial sustainability, implying that sustainability favoured the aged SACCOS. This is probably because long lived SACCOS accumulated enough experiences on marketing of their financial products and also had advantages of reduction of costs. This result are in line with Nyamsogoro (2010) who revealed that age of rural MFIs in Tanzania influence positively the financial sustainability. Similarly, Hartarska and Nadolnyak (2011) found out that age of MFI positively influenced the financial sustainability of MFIs worldwide. However, Bogan (2009) found out that age of MFI negatively influenced the sustainability of MFIs, but the influence was not statistically significant. Moreover, Hermes (2011) found out that older MFIs are less efficient, hence they might be less sustainable too.

Results from Table also show that a cost per borrower reduces the financial sustainability. It implies that rural SACCOS incurred higher cost of loan administration and operation costs which curtailed the financial sustainability. The results are compatible with Kailthya (n.d), Cull et al (2009) and Nyamsogoro (2010) who noted that a greater cost per unit of loan had significantly negative financial performance of MFIs in India, Ethiopia and Tanzania respectively. However, Kipesha and Zhang (2013) noted that reduction of cost per borrower enabled cooperatives MFIs in East Africa to attain the financial sustainability despite lending small sized loans and serving larger proportions of women borrowers.

Furthermore, the findings from Table 2 show that NPL influenced negatively the financial sustainability of the rural SACCOS. The results was confirmed by Magali (2013a) who noted that about 46% rural SACCOS in Morogoro and Dodoma regions were not issuing new loans; some for two years or more because they had large number of NPL and this affected their operations. The problem of huge amounts of NPL for rural SACCOS and cooperatives in Tanzania was also reported by Hakikazi (2006), Bibby (2006), Maghimbi (2010), Mwakajumilo (2011), Karumuna and Akyoo (2011). Contrary, Kereta (2007) found out that despite of having high dependency ratio and NPLs to loan outstanding ratio MFIs were financial sustainable in Ethiopia. However, the study found no evidence of trade-off between outreach and financial sustainability. Similarly as noted by Nyamsogoro (2010) the findings from this study revealed that rural SACCOS in Northern Tanzania performed well in terms of financial sustainability than their counterparts in Central and Eastern zones.

4.3 Descriptive quantative variables for outreach and sustainability

The findings from Table 3 show the descriptive quantative variables for outreach and sustainability. The findings show that the minimum loan for the rural SACCOS was Tshs 20,000. This is the good news for outreach because it complies with the theory of outreach which stresses that the smaller the amount of the loan, the good the outreach (Osotimehin et al 2011; Sheremenko et al (2012); Jegede et al 2012). Also the study noted that the percentage of women clients and borrowers was 42% and 40% respectively, indicating fairly good outreach. On the other hand, the correlation test showed the positive correlation between the female borrowers and ROA, suggesting that female borrowers contributed positively to profitability of the rural SACCOS and hence sustainability. However as noted by Nyamsogoro (2010) and Kipesha (2013), the correlation test showed the positive correlation between the average loan size and cost per borrower, suggesting that the loans were provided at higher costs and this is negative indicator for outreach. However the study noted that the sustainability indicators were not encouraging at all. The findings revealed that 70% of rural SACCOS in Morogoro and Dodoma region were making loss because they lacked effective credits risk mitigation techniques. The study also noted that 17 SACCOS (about 46% of the sample) in Morogoro and Dodoma regions were not issuing new loans from 2006-2013 because they had large number of NPL and hence they lacked capital. Moreover, the study revealed

that the average NPL were 32.38 which was a bit high. Similarly, the study registered a -3.17 and -26.80 of average ROA and ROE respectively (Magali 2013a; Magali (2013b).

Table 2: Regression coefficients for sustainability (measured by OSS)

Independent variables	Estimated value of coefficients	t-value
Grants to Total Loans	-0.248*	-2.769
Log of average loan size	1.312*	7.804
Age of SACCOS	0.223**	2.431
Log of Cost per borrower	-1.439*	-8.760
NPL to Equity	-0.322**	-3.202
Value of R ²	0.760	-
Adjusted R ²	0.722	-
Value of F	19.662*	
Durbin Watson	1.987	-
Standard Error of Estimate	0.15926	-

*Significant at 1% level; **significant at 5% level;

Table 3: Descriptive outreach and sustainability variables

Variables	Value
Minimum loan	20,000 Tshs*
Percentage of women clients	40 %
Percentage of women borrowers	42%
Correlation between log average loan size and log cost per borrower	0.802**
Correlation between women borrowers and ROA	0.4***
Loss making SACCOS	70%
SACCOS which did not disburse new loan between 2006-2013	46%
Average NPL	32.38,
Average ROA	-3.17
Average ROE	-26.80

*Tanzanian Shillings (1 Usd = 1610 Tshs); **Significant at 1% level; ***significant at 5% level

5.0 Conclusion and recommendations

The study revealed that the SACCOS in Eastern and Central zones (Morogoro and Dodoma regions) were in bad condition after phasing out of the capacity building projects which threatened their sustainability. Therefore this study conclude that about than 46% of SACCOS in rural Tanzania especially in Eastern and central zones were not sustainable because they accumulated large number of NPL and they did not issue new loans from 2006-2013. The study further revealed that savings and deposits to total assets influenced the outreach negatively while log cost per borrower and OSS influenced the outreach positively indicating that the rural SACCOS reached many clients including the very poor and women at higher costs while the contribution of savings and deposits to attain higher outreach was negative. Also the study revealed that, grants to total loans, cost per borrower, NPL to equity influenced the sustainability of rural SACCOS negatively while average loan size and age of SACCOS influenced the sustainability of rural SACCOS negatively. Implying that in order the rural SACCOS to attain sustainability they should not rely on grants as recommended by Schreiner (2002), they should increase the size of loan to reduce the costs and should recover all the NPL from their clients. This study further recommends that the rural SACCOS in Tanzania should devise various strategies to achieve financial sustainability such as volunteering labour and accumulate high amounts of own equity in forms of shares as proposed by Gingrich (n.d) who noted that SCCs in Nepal became self sustainable by members' volunteering of their labour and contributing more of their own equity which reduced interest rates and operational costs and it created member participation and ownership. Moreover, I recommend that the rural SACCOS apply credit risks management techniques including insurance coverage to reduce the NPL as proposed by Wenner (2007). Finally I call for policy action to review the operations of rural SACCOS and establish the stringent regulations and supervisions by the government. On the other hand, I recommend for further research with wide coverage to investigate the sustainability of rural SACCOS for the whole Tanzania.

6.0 References

- Abate, G. T., Borzaga, C. and Getnet, K. (2013). Financial sustainability and outreach of microfinance institutions in Ethiopia: does organizational form matter? *Euricse Working Paper n. 56 / 13*.
- Babandi, G. G. (2011). Micro Finance Institutions in Nigeria Outreach and Sustainability: Questionnaire Survey Findings. *International Journal of Business and Social Science, Vol. 2 No. 9*.
- Bibi, A. (2006). Tanzania's Cooperatives Look to the Future. Retrieved from: <http://www.andrewbibby.com/pdf/Tanzania.pdf>, on 13/12/2013.
- Bogan, V. (2009). Capital Structure and Sustainability: An Empirical Study of Microfinance Institutions. Cornell University, NY.
- Bwana, K. M. and Mwakujonga, J. (2013). Issues in SACCOS Development in Kenya and Tanzania: The Historical and Development Perspectives. *Developing Country Studies, Vol.3, No.5, 2013*.
- Conning, J. (2009). Outreach, sustainability and leverage in monitored and peer-monitored lending. *Journal of Development Economics, Vol. 60, 51-77*.
- Cull, R., Demirgüç-Kunt, A. and Morduch, J. (2009). Does Regulatory Supervision Curtail Microfinance Profitability and Outreach? Policy Research Working Paper 4748, The World Bank Development Research Group, Finance and Private Sector Team.
- Gingrich, C. D. (n.d). Community-Based Savings and Credit Cooperatives in Nepal. A Sustainable Means for Microfinance Delivery? *Journal of Microfinance. Volume 6 Number 1:20-39*.
- Haki kazi, (2006). Cooperatives and Development in Tanzania: A Simplified Guide to the Cooperative Development Policy and the Cooperative Societies Act of Tanzania Mainland. Retrieved from: <http://www.hakikazi.org/papers/Cooperatives.pdf>, on 15/01/2014.
- Hartarska, V. and Nadolnyak, D. (2007). Do regulated microfinance institutions achieve better sustainability and outreach? Cross-country evidence. *Applied Economics, 39:10, 1207-1222*.
- Hartarska,V., Mersland, R. and Nadolnyak,D. (n.d). Are Women Better Bankers to the Poor? Evidence from Rural Microfinance Institutions GEL codes: G21, G30, O16.
- Hermes, N. (2009). Microfinance: Its Impact, Outreach, and Sustainability. *World Development Vol. 39, No. 6, pp. 875–881, 2011*.
- Hermes, N., Lensink, R. and Meesters, A. (2008). Outreach and Efficiency of Microfinance Institutions. *World Development Vol. 39, No. 6, pp. 875–881, 2011*.
- Jegade, C.A., Kehinde, J.S. and Akinlabi, B.H.(2012). Trends of Outreach and Sustainability of Microfinance Institutions in Southwestern Nigeria. International Trade & Academic Research Conference (ITARC), 7 – 8th November, 2012, London.UK.
- Kailthya, S. (n.d). Analyzing the Trade-off between Outreach and Financial Performance for Indian Microfinance Institutions. Extension of the Master's thesis at the Madras School of Economics, Chennai.
- Karumuna, L. and Akyoo, A. (2011). Rural Finance Challenges in Tanzania – the case of Kibaigwa Financial Services and Credit Cooperative Society (KIFISACCOS) in Kongwa District. *Business Minds Africa, Case series, number 2 June 2011*.

- Kereta, B.B. (2007). Outreach and Financial Performance Analysis of Microfinance Institutions in Ethiopia. African Economic Conference United Nations Conference Center (UNCC), Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 15-17 November 2007.
- Kinde ,B. A. (2012). Financial Sustainability of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) in Ethiopia. *European Journal of Business and Management, Vol 4, No.15, 2012.*
- Kipasha,F.E. and Zhang, X. (2013). Sustainability, Profitability and Outreach Tradeoffs: Evidences from Microfinance Institutions in East Africa. *European Journal of Business and Management, Vol.5, No.8, 2013.*
- Kumar,V.V and Gupta, V. K. (2011). Analysis of Performance Indicators on Sustenance of Micro Finance Institutes: A Comparative Study of East Asian & Pacific, and South Asian Countries. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting, Vol 2, No 3, 2011.*
- Magali, J.J. (2013a). The Influence of Rural Savings and Credits Cooperatives Societies (SACCOS') Variables on Loans Default Risks: The Case Study of Tanzania. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting, Vol.4, No.19: 77-91.*
- Magali, J.J. (2013b). The Impacts of Credits Risk Management on Profitability of Rural Savings and Credits Cooperative Societies (SACCOS): The Case Study of Tanzania. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research, Vol-2, Issue 12:62-77.*
- Magali, J.J. and Pastory, D. (2013). Technical Efficiency of the Rural Savings and Credits Cooperative Societies in Tanzania: A DEA Approach. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research, Vol-2, Issue 12:49-61.*
- Maghimbi, S. (2010). Cooperatives in Tanzania mainland: Revival and growth. CoopAFRICA Working Paper No.14. *Series on the status of cooperative development in Africa.* International Labour Organization Office in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.
- Mariya, I. Pylypiv, M.S., Strøm, R. Ø. and Oecon (2013). Subsidies and Outreach in Microfinance Institutions.
- Ministry of Finance, Tanzania (MOF 2012; 2013). Speech by the Minister for Finance Hon. Dr. William Augustao Mgemwa (Mp). Introducing to the National Assembly, the Estimates of Government Revenue and Expenditure for the Fiscal Year 2012/2013 and 2013/2014.
- Mohammed, S. (2011). Financing Strategies, Financial Sustainability and Outreach of SACCOS in Uganda. Unpublished MSc. Thesis, University of Makerere.
- Mwakajumilo, (2011). The Role of Informal Microfinance Institutions in Saving Mobilization, Investment and Poverty Reduction. A Case of Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies (SACCOS) in Tanzania from 1961-2008. Unpublished Doctoral Thesis, St. Clements University.
- Ndiege, B.O., Haule, T. B. and Kazungu, I. (2013). Relationship between Sources of Funds and Outreach in Savings and Credits Cooperatives Societies: Tanzanian case. *European Journal of Business and Management, Vol.5, No.9, 2013.*
- Nyamsogoro, D. (2010). Financial Sustainability of Rural Microfinance in Tanzania. Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Greenwich.
- Onumah, E. E. and Acquah,H. D. (2011). Outreach and Sustainability of Inventory Credit Programme in Ghana. *Journal of Agricultural Sciences, Vol. 56, No. 2, 2011, Pages 145-164.*
- Osoimehin, K.O., Jegede, C.A, Akinlabi, B.H. (2011). Determinants of Microfinance Outreach In South-Western Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. *International Journal of Management and Business Studies Vol. 1(1), pp. 001- 007.*

- Pradhan, N. C. (n.d). Microfinance: Issues on Outreach, Sustainability and Ethical Practices. *National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Arts & Education, Volume No.1, Issue No.1*
- Qin, X. and Ndiege, B.O. (2013). Role of Financial Development in Economic Growth: Evidence from Savings and Credits Cooperative Societies in Tanzania. *International Journal of Financial Research, Vol. 4, No. 2; 2013.*
- Quayes, S. (2012). Depth of outreach and financial sustainability of microfinance institutions. *Applied Economics, 2012, 44, 3421–3433.*
- Roy, A. (2012). Is Microfinance Outreach at the cost of profitability? A Case study of the Microfinance Institutions in Assam. *Pacific Business International, Volume 5, Issue 6.*
- Sahoo,S. and Mishra, G. (2012). Outreach and Sustainability of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) through Information Technology: Some Issues and Challenges. *VSRD- International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, Vol. 2 (8), 2012, 694-707.*
- Sarma, G.K. and Borbora, S. (2011). Is Microfinance Outreach Sustainable? A Case of Microfinance Institution Model in India. Paper prepared for “Second European Research Conference on Microfinance”to be held during June 16-June 18, 2011: University of Groningen, The Netherlands.
- Schreiner, M. (2002). Aspects of Outreach: A Framework for the Discussion of the Social Benefits of Microfinance. *Journal of International Development, Vol. 14, pp. 1-13.*
- Sebhatu, K.T. (2011). Management of Savings and Credit Cooperatives from the Perspective of Outreach and Sustainability: Evidence from Southern Tigray of Ethiopia. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting, Vol 2, No 7/8, 2011.*
- Seibel, H. D. and Parhusip, U. (1998). Attaining Outreach with Sustainability. A Case Study of a Private Micro-Finance Institution in Indonesia. *IDS Bulletin Vol 29 No 4 1998.*
- Sheremenko, G., Cesar L. E. and Florkowski, W.J.(2012).The Universality of Microfinance Operations Model in Eastern Europe and Central Asia: Financial Sustainability vs. Poverty. Selected Paper prepared for presentation at the Agricultural & Applied Economics Association’s 2012 AAEA Annual Meeting, Seattle, Washington, August 12-14, 2012.
- Temu, S.S. and Ishengoma, E.K. (2010). Financial Linkages and Performance of Rural Microfinance Cooperatives: Tanzanian Case. *Indian Journal of Economics and Business, Vol. 9. No.2.*
- Thapa, G. (n.d).Sustainability and Governance of Microfinance Institutions: Recent Experiences and Some Lessons for Southeast Asia. *Asian Journal of Agriculture and Development, Vol. 4, No. 1:17-37.*
- Wangwe, S. (2004). Innovation in Rural Finance in Tanzania. Paper prepared for The Third Annual Conference on Microfinance held from 15th to 17th March 2004 at the AICC, Arusha, Tanzania.
- Wenner, M., Navajas, S., Trivelli, C. and Tarazona, A. (2007). Managing Credit Risk in Rural Financial Institutions in Latin America, Inter-American Development Bank.
- Woller, G.M., Dunford, C. and Woodworth, W. (1999). Where to Microfinance? *International Journal of Economic Development, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 29-64.*
- Yaron, J. and Manos, R. (2007). Determining the Self Sufficiency of Microfinance Institutions, *Savings & Development, No. 2, pp 131-160.*

Zaigham, R. and Asghar, N. (2011). Sustainability of Micro Finance Banks: A comparative Case study from Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Vol 3, No 8:570-584.*

Zeller M. and Meyer, R. L. (2002). The Triangle of Microfinance: Financial Sustainability, Outreach and Impact. International Food Policy Research Institute Washington, D.C. Number 40, November 2002.

Zerai, B. and Rani L. (2013). Is There a Tradeoff between Outreach and Sustainability of Micro finance institutions? Evidence from Indian Microfinance Institutions (MFIs). *European Journal of Business and Management, Vol 4, No.2, 2012.*

8. Appendices

8.1 Outreach model

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.928 ^a	.861	.843	.14033	1.847

a. Predictors: (Constant), Savings and deposits to total assets, Age of SACCOS, Log cost per borrower, OSS

b. Dependent Variable: Logaverageloans

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.893	4	.973	49.420	.000 ^a
	Residual	.630	32	.020		
	Total	4.523	36			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Savings and deposits to total assets, Age of SACCOS, Log cost per borrower, OSS

b. Dependent Variable: Logaverageloan

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.463	.309		4.735	.000		
	Log cost per borrower	.866	.064	1.032	1.353E1	.000	.747	1.338
	OSS	.548	.090	.467	6.070	.000	.737	1.357
	Age of SACCOS	-.011	.007	-.115	-1.558	.129	.800	1.249
	Savings and deposits to total assets	-.183	.075	-.183	-2.449	.020	.779	1.283

a. Dependent Variable: Logaverageloans

8.2 Sustainability model

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.872 ^a	.760	.722	.15926	1.987

a. Predictors: (Constant), NPL to Equity, Log of Cost per borrowers, Age of SACCOS, Grants to Total Loans, Log of average loan size

b. Dependent Variable: Financial Self Sufficiency

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.494	5	.499	19.662	.000 ^a
	Residual	.786	31	.025		
	Total	3.280	36			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Grants to Total Loans, Log of average loan size, Age of SACCOS, Log of Cost per borrower, NPL to Equity

b. Dependent Variable: Financial Self Sufficiency

Coefficient^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.968	.446		-2.169	.038		
	Grants to Total Loans	-.011	.004	-.248	-2.769	.009	.965	1.036
	Log of average loan size	1.117	.143	1.312	7.804	.000	.274	3.656
	Age of SACCOS	.017	.007	.223	2.431	.021	.923	1.084
	Log of Cost per borrower	-1.028	.117	-1.439	-8.760	.000	.287	3.490
	NPL to Equity	-.024	.007	-.322	-3.202	.003	.762	1.311

a. Dependent Variable: Financial Self Sufficiency

8.3.1 Correlation Tests

Correlations

		Women borrowed	ROA
Women borrowed	Pearson Correlation	1	.400*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.014
	N	37	37

ROA	Pearson Correlation	.400*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.014	
	N	37	37

8.3.2 Correlations

		Financial Self Sufficiency	Grants to Total Loans	Age of SACCOS	Log of Cost per borrowers	Log of average loan size	NPL to Equity
Financial Self Sufficiency	Pearson Correlation	1	-.145	.361	-.323	.149	.050
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.390	.028	.051	.379	.770
	N	37	37	37	37	37	37
Grants to Total Loans	Pearson Correlation	-.145	1	.049	-.072	-.043	-.137
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.390		.774	.672	.801	.419
	N	37	37	37	37	37	37
Age of SACCOS	Pearson Correlation	.361	.049	1	.070	.164	-.111
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.028	.774		.681	.332	.511
	N	37	37	37	37	37	37
Log of Cost per borrowers	Pearson Correlation	-.323	-.072	.070	1	.802	-.094
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.051	.672	.681		.000	.579
	N	37	37	37	37	37	37
Log of average loan size	Pearson Correlation	.149	-.043	.164	.802	1	.173
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.379	.801	.332	.000		.305
	N	37	37	37	37	37	37
NPL to Equity	Pearson Correlation	.050	-.137	-.111	-.094	.173	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.770	.419	.511	.579	.305	
	N	37	37	37	37	37	37

8.4 Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity was diagnosed by comparing the coefficients of calculated and observed chi square. The results show that calculated chi square $NXR^2 \rightarrow 0.706 * 37 = 26.122$ at 0.05 significance level is $< \chi^2(37) = 50.998$ from chi square table, implying that there is no heteroskedasticity in the model (Magali, 2013a).